

1 KIOS CoE – Sandboxing use-case 4 (SUC4) – Coordinated Overcurrent Protection

1.1 Description

Power system is a critical infrastructure vulnerable to short-circuit faults that needs to be timely detected and cleared by the protection schemes in order to ensure the reliable and safe operation of the system. For this reason, intelligent electronic devices (IED) functioning as protection relays and equipped with different protection algorithms are utilized at each part of the power infrastructure to protect its critical components. In this SUC, the overcurrent protective relays are used as IEDs operating in a coordinated manner, where they communicate with each other within a substation to timely and effectively isolate the fault while minimizing load shedding.

Figure 1: Testbed setup for the overcurrent protection scheme.

A coordinated overcurrent protection is presented in this SUC, featuring communication between upstream (IED1) and downstream IEDs (IED2, IED3), as depicted in Figure 1. These overcurrent relays were incorporated in a selected transmission substation, emulated within the digital twin model running in the real-time simulator. The primary function of an IED acting as an overcurrent protective relay is to protect substations from high current faults during short-circuit events. When a short-circuit fault occurs within the distribution feeder protected by IED2, high currents are detected by both downstream (e.g., IED2) and upstream (e.g., IED1) relays. In a typical non-coordinated overcurrent protection scheme, it is challenging to ensure a timely response and proper discrimination, where the relay closest to the fault needs to trip first (to minimize the out-of-service customers). Consequently, coordinated overcurrent protection schemes have been introduced to achieve a rapid response with appropriate discrimination.

Under a coordinated overcurrent approach, when a downstream IED (e.g., IED2) detects high current (i.e., the current measurement exceeds a specified threshold), it waits a few milliseconds

before sending a trip command to CB2 to open and clear the fault. Simultaneously, IED2 sends a fault-detection and block message, which is subscribed (read) by IED1. As a result, IED1 is blocked from tripping CB1, prioritizing the operation of the downstream relay closer to the fault, and preventing unnecessary tripping of all downstream feeders, which would cause undesired regional blackouts with more consumers out-of-service. However, if CB2 fails to operate, IED2 cancels the block and sends an inter-trip message to the upstream backup IED (e.g., IED1), requesting it to trip its CB (i.e., CB1) as back-up protection to ensure fault clearing during a CB failure. This exchange of messages between IEDs is facilitated by the GOOSE protocol, defined by the IEC 61850 standard for fast and reliable communication in substations, enabling protection and automation. High-speed communication (below the critical time of 3 ms) is achieved via GOOSE, resulting in the exchange of critical information and timely, accurate detection and isolation of electrical faults.

To better understand this sandboxing use case related to cyber-attacks on GOOSE messages that affect the response of coordinated overcurrent relays, a closer analysis of the GOOSE protocol is provided. The structure of a GOOSE message has a specific format and consists of two primary parts, the communication-frame data and the control-frame data. The communication-frame data (i.e., the Ethernet frame) contains the network-related information necessary for the transmission of the message over the network. This includes the following fields:

- *Destination MAC Address*: Represents the multicast MAC address that allows multiple IEDs to receive the message, ensuring it reaches all intended devices on the network.
- *Source MAC Address*: The MAC address of the IED that publishes the message, distinguishing the different physical devices in the network.

The control-frame data, also known as the GOOSE Protocol Data Unit (PDU), is the payload of the message and contains specific information related to the event or state being communicated. Some of the fields included in the PDU are:

- *GOOSE Identifier (goID)*: A unique identifier within the GOOSE message that distinguishes different types of messages sent on the same multicast MAC address, ensuring that the correct IEDs subscribe to the correct GOOSE messages.
- *State Number (stNum)*: An integer number that increments with each new state change (e.g., detection of a fault, sending a trip command to the CB, detection of a CB failure, sending an inter-trip command, clearing of a fault, etc.) in the publisher (i.e., every time a new message is published).
- *Sequence Number (sqNum)*: An integer number that increments with each re-transmission of the same state.
- *allData*: Contains the actual data values being communicated, which could include binary information or analogue measurements. In this SUC, four binary values were used: fault (F), inter-trip (T), block (B), and CB failure (CBF), representing the detection of a fault, sending of an inter-trip command, sending of a block command, and detection of a CB failure, respectively.

GOOSE messages are being multicast to a selected group of devices that have subscribed to the multicast group (i.e., destination MAC address). In this SUC, all the IEDs are using the same destination MAC address (since all are emulated within the real time simulator), but each published message has a unique goID, as listed in Table 1. FDI or MS cyber-attacks are made possible when the attacker is connected to the same network and uses the same Destination MAC address of the target group to capture the messages that are being communicated. This way the attacker is able

to copy the GOOSE structure, identify the current state and event and perform a precise attack by spoofing the desired gold. The fake message can be a copy or a modified version of the spoofed message.

Table 1: IEC 6180/GOOSE communication.

gold	Destination MAC Address	Published by (IED name / Source MAC Address)	Subscribed by
gold1	01-0C-CD-01-28-58	IED1 / AC:1F:6B:69:C4:35, <i>Attacker</i>	IED2, IED3, <i>Attacker</i>
gold2	01-0C-CD-01-28-58	IED2 / 00:26:55:DC:CD:CF, <i>Attacker</i>	IED1, IED3, <i>Attacker</i>

In this context, an attacker can follow a false data injection (FDI) or a message suppression (MS) approach in order to affect the operation of the coordinated protection scheme. As it is presented in the following sub-section, a cyber-attack in this framework can either cause an undesired relay tripping that leads to a regional blackout or prevent a relay tripping during a short-circuit fault that is able to initiate catastrophic failure to power infrastructure.

1.2 Attack scenarios

The attack scenarios that are demonstrated in this SUC focus on two primary types of attacks on IEC 61850/GOOSE: one involving FDI to intentionally trip a protection relay during normal operation (without a short-circuit event), and another involving MS attack to prevent the back-up protection relay tripping during a short-circuit event combined with a CB failure. The attacks investigated in this SUC are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Attack Vector for SUC4

Attack Vector	Description
Attacked devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GOOSE signal exchange between virtual IEDs (protection relays) emulated within the sandboxing environment
Protocols	IEC 61850/GOOSE
Type of attack	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> False Data Injection (FDI) Message Suppression (MS)
Attack vector	Attacker should have access to local network and to specific multicast groups
Complexity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FDI: High complexity attack targeting the data payload within the GOOSE messages. Requires deep knowledge of the GOOSE data structure and context, and understanding of how specific devices (i.e., relays) interpret and act on GOOSE messages, in order to inject plausible false data. This scenario is demonstrated when CBs are healthy (without a mechanical failure), under normal operation (no attack) and under FDI attack. MS: High complexity attack targeting the status/sequence number of GOOSE messages. Requires basic knowledge of the protocol to identify critical messages, and understanding the role of status and sequence numbers, as well as how devices handle and validate these numbers, in order to disrupt the normal processing of messages without necessarily altering the content itself. This attack is synchronized with a CB failure event that needs to be timely recognized by the attacker in order to maximize the impact of this cyber-attack. The operation of this scenario is demonstrated under normal (no attack) conditions and under a MS attack.
Privileges required	The attack is launched either virtually within the digital twin or at the network level without requiring any privileges (e.g., administration rights) to access the device.
User interaction	None - There is no requirement for the attacker to authenticate to launch the attack.

1.3 Analysis of results

In this section, two selected scenarios (S1-S2) related to SUC4 are demonstrated and analysed, considering some cyber-attacks on the local network affecting the virtual IEDs that are modelled within the digital twin model. An attacker model running in the real-time simulator is connected to the local network as well, to perform FDI and MS attacks. For each scenario, indicative plots are provided to illustrate the operation of SUC4 under each attack, along with a detailed impact assessment for each scenario.

1.3.1 SUC4/S1 – FDI cyber-attack on GOOSE signals when CB is healthy

The first scenario (S1) of SUC4 examines the operation of the substation’s overcurrent protection scheme when all the circuit breakers (CBs) are healthy. This subsection compares the appropriate operation of the protection scheme (without any cyber-attack) to its operation under a False Data Injection (FDI) cyber-attack. FDI attacks involve injecting deceptive data into the communication stream, causing the IEDs to take incorrect actions based on misleading information. In this scenario, the FDI attack is initiated by an attacker model that injects fake messages into the local network (e.g., false tripping signals), targeting the destination MAC address of the IEDs. The results are demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Coordinated overcurrent protection scheme operation with healthy CBs under normal operation (without attack) and under FDI attack causing undesired relay tripping: (a) Status number (stNum) of IED2 and attacker; (b) GOOSE message (F, T, B, CBF) published by IED2; (c) GOOSE message (F, T, B, CBF) published by attacker; (d) status of circuit breakers (1=closed, 0=open); (e) instantaneous current injection through IED1 during normal operation; (f) instantaneous current injection through IED1 during an FDI attack.

1.3.1.1 Normal operation (without cyber-attack on GOOSE)

During normal operation, a short-circuit fault occurs at 12.95 s within the downstream feeder where IED2 is located, causing an increased current that exceeds a predefined threshold, as shown in Figure 2 (e). The overcurrent conditions are sensed by the overcurrent relays of both the downstream (IED2) and upstream (IED1) feeders. Since IED2 is closer to the fault, it is responsible for acting first and clearing the fault, as defined by the protection scheme objective. As shown in Figure 2 (b), IED2 detects the fault event and sends a GOOSE message with $F=1$. Then, a trip signal commands CB2 to open, while IED2 blocks the upstream relay (IED1) by sending a block message with $B=1$ to prevent the unnecessary tripping of CB1. Since CB2 is healthy in this scenario, it opens at 13.1 s, as shown in Figure 2 (d), the fault is cleared, and only the downstream feeder is out-of-service (causing a blackout to a minimum number of consumers as the fault is cleared by the relay closest to the fault). This is demonstrated by the reduced current injection of the upstream feeder in Figure 2 (e). IED2 sends a fault-cleared message ($F=0$) while still blocking IED1. Every time IED2 detects a new event and publishes a new GOOSE message, it increments its publisher state by changing the $stNum$, as depicted in Figure 2 (a). Hence, without the presence of a cyber-attack, the coordinated protection scheme is able to clear the fault promptly to protect the substation equipment while achieving proper discrimination, ensuring the fault is cleared by the closest relay.

1.3.1.2 FDI cyber-attack on GOOSE signals

To examine the effect of a cyber-attack in this context, an FDI attack is launched using the attacker model, which is also connected to the local network. The aim of this attack is to mislead IED1 into unnecessarily tripping CB1, without detecting any overcurrent fault. The attacker subscribes to the same destination MAC address as the IEDs to capture the GOOSE messages and analyze their structure and content. To deceive IED1, the attacker publishes a message that IED1 will subscribe to by spoofing $gold2$. The attacker captures this message and manipulates the “*allData*” field by modifying the desired data attribute value, specifically the binary value of the “*Inter-Trip*” variable, to be equal to 1 ($T=1$). Additionally, the attacker increases the value of the “*stNum*” field so that it will overwrite all incoming benign messages with lower $stNum$ values, effectively ignoring all messages sent by IED2 after the attack is launched, as the IED logic accepts only GOOSE messages with $stNum$ higher than previously received messages. As shown in Figure 2 (a) and (c), the attacker publishes the fake message at 8.35 s, during normal grid conditions (without any short-circuit fault). IED1 receives the attacker’s message and recognizes it as a benign message coming from IED2. Due to the high $stNum$ (e.g., equals to 5) of the fake message, depicted in Figure 2 (a), all incoming messages from IED2 that were supposed to be subscribed to by IED1 are now ignored, as shown in the grey area of Figure 2 (b). Consequently, the protective relay is controlled by the fake inter-trip signal, causing IED1 to command CB1 to trip, as depicted in Figure 2 (d), resulting in an undesired regional blackout of all downstream feeders, as indicated by the zero current injection in Figure 2 (f).

The impact assessment of this FDI attack indicates that injecting a false trip signal during normal grid conditions can cause protection relays to take erroneous actions, unnecessarily disconnecting parts of the power grid and leading to regional blackout scenarios. Furthermore, false commands and improper operation of devices or equipment can potentially cause damage to transformers, circuit breakers, or other power infrastructure. It should be noted that any other messages sent to the attacked IED by the rest of the IEDs are ignored due to the high value of $stNum$, leading to improper and uncontrolled operation of the coordinated protection scheme during such attacks.

1.3.2 SUC4/S2 – MS cyber-attack on GOOSE signals when CB presents failure

The second scenario (S2) of SUC4 examines the operation of the substation's protection scheme when CB2 fails and cannot operate (open) to clear the fault. This case compares the normal operation of the protection scheme (without any cyber-attack) to its operation under a Message Suppression (MS) attack. MS attacks involve intentionally preventing benign messages from being delivered to their intended recipients. The attacker suppresses legitimate critical messages by making them appear outdated or irrelevant, thereby delaying or preventing them from reaching their destination. In this scenario, the MS attack is initiated by an attacker model injecting fake messages into the local network, targeting the destination MAC address of the IEDs. The results are demonstrated in Figure 3.

1.3.2.1 Normal operation (without cyber-attack on GOOSE)

During normal operation (without any cyber-attack), a short-circuit fault occurs at 14.85 s in the downstream feeder where IED2 is installed, causing an increased current that exceeds a predefined threshold, as shown in Figure 3 (e). The overcurrent conditions are detected by the overcurrent relays in both the downstream (IED2) and upstream (IED1) feeders. Since IED2 is located closer to the fault, it is primarily responsible for taking action and clearing the fault first to achieve the required discrimination by the protection scheme, isolating the fault with the closest relay. As depicted in Figure 3 (b), IED2 publishes a GOOSE message with $F=1$ as soon as the fault is detected. Following this, a trip signal requests CB2 to open, while IED2 prevents the upstream relay (IED1) from tripping by sending a block message with $B=1$. However, due to a failure in CB2 (CB2 status in Figure 3 (d) remains closed and equals to 1), the breaker cannot trip, and the fault still persists. IED2 detects this mechanical failure and stops the blocking message (i.e., $B=0$), instead publishing a message indicating a CB failure (i.e., $CBF=1$) and requesting an inter-trip (i.e., $T=1$) from the backup protection relay, as indicated in see Figure 3 (b). IED1 receives this message and commands CB1 to trip as backup protection. When CB1 opens, as it is demonstrated in Figure 3 (d) at 15.07 s, a regional blackout occurs in all the downstream feeders, which is necessary to clear the fault, as indicated by the zero current injection in Figure 3 (e). Once IED2 detects no overcurrent fault, it stops the inter-trip and publishes a message with the new event (i.e., $F=0$, $T=0$). Whenever IED2 detects a new event and issues a new GOOSE message, it updates its publisher state by incrementing the $stNum$, as shown in Figure 3 (a). The coordinated protection scheme effectively utilizes backup protection to promptly clear the fault, thereby protecting the power infrastructure, even when CB2 presents a mechanical failure.

1.3.2.2 MS cyber-attack on GOOSE signals

On the other hand, when an MS attack is performed under a short-circuit event combined with a mechanical failure in CB2, the operation of the protection scheme can be critically affected. In this scenario, an MS attack is launched using an attacker model connected to the local network. The aim of this attack is to prevent IED1 from receiving critical messages, such as the inter-trip message that activates the backup protection. The attacker first captures the GOOSE messages in the communication stream by subscribing to the same destination MAC address as the IEDs. Then, the attacker spoofs the identifier of IED2 by using a message with $goID2$ to publish a message to IED1, the target of the attack. The attacker modifies the $stNum$ value of the PDU to be high enough to ensure that no other benign message in the multicast group can have a higher $stNum$ value. This ensures that the fake message will overwrite all incoming benign messages with a lower $stNum$. It is noted that the IED logic considers valid only messages with an $stNum$ higher than the latest

received message. Therefore, injecting a message with a higher *stNum* will cause the IED to ignore forthcoming benign messages. The higher the *stNum* of the fake message, the greater the delay in receiving a benign message.

Since the “allData” field is not modified as in the case of an FDI attack in SUC4/S1, the timing of the fake message injection plays a critical role in the success of the MS attack in this scenario. As shown in Figure 3 (a) and (c), the fake message is published by the attacker at around 14.9 s, right before IED2 is about to send the inter-trip message. This can be achieved either by using a time-based triggered attack, selecting the exact time of the attack, or using an event-based triggered attack, where the attack is initiated after a specific event. In this case, the *B=1* event can be detected and trigger the event-based attack, as it is the last event before the inter-trip message, as depicted in Figure 3 (b). The high *stNum* of the fake message (higher than the previous received benign message) deceives IED1 into accepting the attacker's message as a benign message supposedly published by IED2, causing all actual benign messages from IED2 to be suppressed, as shown in the grey area of Figure 3 (b). As a result, IED1 is controlled by the fake message depicted in Figure 3 (c), which includes no inter-trip signal.

Figure 3: Coordinated overcurrent protection scheme operation when a CB present a mechanical failure under normal operation (without attack) and under MS cyber-attack. (a) Status number (*stNum*) of IED2 and attacker; (b) GOOSE message (F, T, B, CBF) published by IED2; (c) GOOSE message (F, T, B, CBF) published by attacker; (d) status of circuit breakers (1=closed, 0=open); (e) instantaneous current injection through IED1 during normal operation; (f) instantaneous current injection through IED1 during an MS attack.

Consequently, IED2 continues requesting backup protection, while IED1, receiving block messages from the attacker, takes no protective action. With CB2 mechanically failed and the message to activate the backup protection suppressed by the cyber-attack, the short-circuit fault is not cleared neither by the primary nor backup protection. Therefore, the overcurrent conditions persist as it is shown in Figure 3 (f), leading to a prolonged fault that will inevitably cause serious damage to the power infrastructure.

The impact assessment of the MS attack in this scenario indicates that discarding legitimate messages can lead to the loss of critical control or protection signals, while delaying messages can cause delayed detection and response to faults or abnormal conditions in the power grid, potentially worsening the impact of incidents. During faults, delayed or suppressed messages increase the risk of damaging the power infrastructure, as outage durations are prolonged and system vulnerability is increased.

1.4 Datasets

Two main scenarios (S1-S2) related to SUC4 operation have been demonstrated in the previous section. The first scenario explores the response of the coordinated overcurrent protection when CBs are healthy, under normal operation, i.e., SUC4/S1(without attack), and the under a FDI cyber-attack on GOOSE communication protocol, i.e., SUC4/S1(with FDI attack). Similarly, the scenario investigates the response of the coordinated overcurrent protection when there a mechanical failure in the CB of the downstream feeder, under normal operation, i.e., SUC4/S2(without attack), and the under a MS cyber-attack on GOOSE protocol, i.e., SUC4/S2(with MS attack). Details regarding the datasets captured during the execution of each scenario (with and without attacks), including electrical measurements and network traffic, are described in Table 3-Table 6. The datasets from each scenario of SUC4 are made openly available and can be accessed through Zenodo repository.

Table 3: SUC4/S1(without attack) datasets

SUC4/S1	Normal operation (without cyber-attack on GOOSE) when CBs are healthy
Dataset description	<p>This dataset is related to the operation of the sandboxing use case SUC4 described in this document, which examines operation of the protection scheme in a substation using overcurrent protective relays (IEDs) in the sandboxing environment, that communicate with each other via IEC6180/GOOSE protocol. Specifically, this dataset corresponds to the first scenario (S1) of SUC4, without any attack. More details about the scenario related to this dataset can be found in Section 1.3.1 of this supporting document.</p> <p>The dataset includes electrical measurements of the upstream and downstream feeders of the substation, the status (stNum) and sequence (sqNum) numbers, along with the binary values in “alldata” field of the GOOSE messages of IED1 and IED2, as well as the status of the CB1 and CB2. The dataset is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and CSV (.csv) files. The measurements were recorded with a 0.5-millisecond time resolution by specific blocks in RT-Lab environment of the real time simulator. In addition, network traffic data as Packer CAPture files (.pcapng) are included in this database.</p>
Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the operation of overcurrent protective relays operating as IEDs and communicating with IEC618050/GOOSE protocol, under normal operation without cyber-attacks, when all CBs are healthy. To be used as a base reference for comparison with cases where cyber-attacks take place, to enable an impact assessment for related cyber-attacks.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [Electron_SUC4_S1_Without_Attack_Measurements.mat] [Electron_SUC4_S1_Without_Attack_Measurements.csv]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [Electron_SUC4_S1_Without_Attack_Traffic.pcapng]
File size	17 KB, 43 KB
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrical measurements and GOOSE signals are extracted from the digital twin (running within the real-time simulators) of the sandboxing environment, using a block in the RT-LAB library named as 'OpWrite'. All the network traffic related to IEC 61850/GOOSE communication is captured by the WireShark software.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current (in A) from upstream and downstream feeders, binary values as GOOSE message data, and network packets in the format of IEC61850/GOOSE packets.
Metadata and keywords	Overcurrent protective relays, intelligent electronic devices, digital substation, virtual power plant, substation automation, cyber-attacks, multicast, Destination MAC Address, goID, false data injection, IEC 61850, GOOSE, electrical measurements, current measurements, signals, circuit breakers.

Table 4: SUC4/S1(with FDI attack) datasets

SUC4/S1	FDI cyber-attack on GOOSE signals when CBs are healthy
Dataset description	<p>This dataset corresponds to the first scenario (S1) of SUC4, where an FDI cyber-attack is conducted in the local network by an attacker model, in order to inject fake messages to deceive an IED to unnecessarily trip its CB during normal grid conditions (without a short-circuit event) and cause a regional blackout. More details about the scenario related to this dataset can be found in Section 1.3.1 of the supporting document.</p> <p>The dataset includes electrical measurements of the upstream and downstream feeders of the substation, the status (stNum) and sequence (sqNum) numbers, along with the binary values in "alldata" field of the GOOSE messages of IED1 and IED2, as well as the status of the CB1 and CB2. The dataset is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and CSV (.csv) files. The measurements were recorded with a 0.5-millisecond time resolution by specific blocks in RT-Lab environment of the real time simulator. In addition, network traffic data as Packer CAPture files (.pcapng) are included in this database.</p>
Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the operation of overcurrent protective relays operating as IEDs and communicating with IEC618050/GOOSE protocol, under FDI attack, when all CBs are healthy. Perform an impact assessment of cyber-attacks in such smart grid applications. Test and evaluate cyber-security solutions to prevent attacks' impact on power infrastructure.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [Electron_SUC4_S1_FDI_Attack_Measurements.mat] [Electron_SUC4_S1_FDI_Attack_Measurements.csv] [Electron_SUC4_S1_FDI_Attack_Traffic.pcapng]
File size	17 KB, 43 KB
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrical measurements and GOOSE signals are extracted from the digital twin (running within the real-time simulators) of the sandboxing environment, using a block in the RT-LAB library named as 'OpWrite'. All the network traffic related to IEC 61850/GOOSE communication is captured by the WireShark software.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current (in A) from upstream and downstream feeders, binary values as GOOSE message data, and network packets in the format of IEC61850/GOOSE packets.
Metadata and keywords	Overcurrent protective relays, intelligent electronic devices, digital substation, virtual power plant, substation automation, cyber-attacks, multicast, Destination MAC Address, goID, false data injection, IEC 61850, GOOSE, electrical measurements, current measurements, signals, circuit breakers.

Table 5: SUC4/S2(without attack) datasets

SUC4/S2	Normal operation (without attack on GOOSE) when CB presents a failure
Dataset description	<p>This dataset corresponds to the second scenario (S2) of SUC4, without any attack. More details about the scenario related to this dataset can be found in Section 1.3.2 of the supporting document.</p> <p>The dataset includes electrical measurements of the upstream and downstream feeders of the substation, the status (stNum) and sequence (sqNum) numbers, along with the binary values in “alldata” field of the GOOSE messages of IED1 and IED2, as well as the status of the CB1 and CB2. The dataset is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and .csv files. The measurements were recorded with a 0.5-millisecond time resolution by specific blocks in RT-Lab environment of the real time simulator. In addition, network traffic data as Packer CAPture files (.pcapng) are included in this database.</p>
Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the operation of overcurrent protective relays operating as IEDs and communicating with IEC618050/GOOSE protocol, under normal operation without cyber-attacks, when a mechanical CB failure occurs. To be used as a base reference for comparison with cases where cyber-attacks take place, to enable an impact assessment for related cyber-attacks.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [Electron_SUC4_S2_Without_Attack_Measurements.mat] [Electron_SUC4_S2_Without_Attack_Measurements.csv] [Electron_SUC4_S2_Without_Attack_Traffic.pcapng]
File size	17 KB, 43 KB
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrical measurements and GOOSE signals are extracted from the digital twin (running within the real-time simulators) of the sandboxing environment, using a block in the RT-LAB library named as ‘OpWrite’. All the network traffic related to IEC 61850/GOOSE communication is captured by the WireShark software.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current (in A) from upstream and downstream feeders, binary values as message data, and network packets in the format of IEC61850/GOOSE packets.
Metadata and keywords	Overcurrent protective relays, intelligent electronic devices, digital substation, virtual power plant, substation automation, cyber-attacks, multicast, Destination MAC Address, gold, message suppression, IEC 61850, GOOSE, electrical measurements, current measurements, signals, circuit breakers.

Table 6: SUC4/S2(with MS attack) datasets

SUC4/S2	MS cyber-attack on GOOSE signals when CB presents a failure.
Dataset description	<p>This dataset corresponds to the second scenario (S2) of SUC4, where an MS cyber-attack is conducted in the local network in order prevent critical benign messages, such inter-trip messages requesting backup protection, to reach their destination (back-up IED) when a CB failure occurs during a short-circuit event. As a result, the duration of a short-circuit is prolonged or the protection scheme is not able to clear the short-circuit event, which can cause catastrophic failures to power system. More details about the scenario related to this dataset can be found in Section 1.3.2 of the support document.</p> <p>The dataset includes electrical measurements of the upstream and downstream feeders of the substation, the status (stNum) and sequence (sqNum) numbers, along with the binary values in “alldata” field of the GOOSE messages of IED1 and IED2, as well as the status of the CB1 and CB2. The dataset is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and CSV (.csv) files. The measurements were recorded with a 0.5-millisecond time resolution by specific blocks in RT-Lab environment of the real time simulator. In addition, network traffic data as Packer CAPture files (.pcapng) are included in this database.</p>

Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the operation of overcurrent protective relays operating as IEDs and communicating with IEC618050/GOOSE protocol, under a MS attack, when a mechanical CB failure occurs. Perform an impact assessment of cyber-attacks in such smart grid applications. Test and evaluate cyber-security solutions to prevent attacks' impact on power infrastructure.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [Electron_SUC4_S2_MS_Attack_Measurements.mat] [Electron_SUC4_S2_MS_Attack_Measurements.csv] [Electron_SUC4_S2_MS_Attack_Traffic.pcapng]
File size	17 KB, 43 KB
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrical measurements and GOOSE signals are extracted from the digital twin (running within the real-time simulators) of the sandboxing environment, using a block in the RT-LAB library named as 'OpWrite'. All the network traffic related to IEC 61850/GOOSE communication is captured by the WireShark software.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current (in A) from upstream and downstream feeders, binary values as message data, and network packets in the format of IEC61850/GOOSE packets.
Metadata and keywords	Overcurrent protective relays, intelligent electronic devices, digital substation, virtual power plant, substation automation, cyber-attacks, multicast, Destination MAC Address, goID, message suppression, IEC 61850, GOOSE, electrical measurements, current measurements, signals, circuit breakers.